

Responses to the Editor's and Peer Reviewers' comments:

Comment	Response
Comments about the minimum required information	
#1. Whilst a cover letter was provided, it did not use the correct template and therefore some required information about the submission is missing. The correct template can be found here.	Cover letter using the template was uploaded to Zenodo.
#2. Full name and affiliations of all co-authors have been provided but their ORCID's (if available) are missing both on ScholarOne and Zenodo.	ORCID's have been added to Zenodo and Scholar One.
#7. Informative disclosure of interests have been provided for all co-authors on the ScholarOne system but not uploaded to Zenodo. Could you please add the document to your Zenodo record? As this is a public record, the authors who have declared no intellectual interest may want an opportunity to revise their declaration.	Thank you for spotting; we added the Declarations to Zenodo. As we note below in the response to a Peer Reviewer, we acknowledge that some authors' Dols are more extensive than others. We queried those co-authors who provided more concise forms about additional disclosures, however, they did not feel they had anything to add.
#12. Please indicate the preregistration level in the resubmitted cover letter	This information was added to the cover letter in Zenodo.
Structured assessment	
1. I like the protocol; it is concise and clear.	Thank you very much.
2. The rationale for conducting the study is clearly and succinctly explained.	Thank you very much.
3. General comment, can you expand on how other SR frameworks that are available for specifically toxicology discuss grey literature such as NTP OHAT, EFSA, EPA/TSCA, WHO?	Thank you for this suggestion. We added both the definitions/examples, and processes around searching for grey literature, from the EPA and National Toxicology Programme guidance.
4. The authors cite one reference to support the claim that ignoring grey literature may be detrimental to SRs. The citation used is not appropriate and is hardly a piece of evidence in favour of using the grey literature (e.g., LL7-9 on p. 8 - here (12) is used, but I find it inappropriate as a supporting text for the claims in sentences). Is there any other evidence or conceptual work on the role/potential of grey literature?	We reframed the need for our work as a need to understand how individuals conducting evidence syntheses in EHT deal with grey literature, in light of the many challenges long identified with doing so. We provided additional examples and references to clarify the challenges around the searching and dealing with grey literature.
5. The knowledge goals of the survey are clear.	Thank you very much.
6. The problem of 'grey literature' is an important one - solving it may potentially reduce publication bias but may also introduce all sorts of other sources of bias to systematic reviews.	We agree. The grey literature aspect of systematic reviews has been methodologically neglected, compared to other aspects (screening, data extraction, searching databases). The present survey is a starting point for what we hope is further methodological work in this space.
7. An aspect of grey literature that is challenging is the extent to which grey literature is also identified as proper peer-reviewed literature (e.g., PhD theses that also happen to be later published, sometimes under different titles or otherwise hard to link to original theses). Is the protocol going to address this or attempt to quantify the extent of this issue?	We agree that PhD theses are a tricky due to the potential double counting of evidence issue (many PhD students publish at least parts of their theses in journals). We do ask in content questions 1 and 2 about theses and dissertations. Informal checks amongst our colleagues suggest that dissertations are treated like preprints - where identified, search experts

	check if there is a published version. How many take this approach, and what other approaches are adopted is beyond the scope of this survey, but this a very interesting question that absolutely needs answering.
Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding: More detail on the thematic analysis would be beneficial. At the moment, it is not fully clear if the authors intend to use a deductive coding strategy, an inductive strategy, or a combination of the two. How the coding will generate data that is analysable for the research goals should also be specified.	Thank you for flagging this. We have amended the manuscript to provide more detail in line with the responses below, to Peer Reviewer Comment #13.
8. The methods for survey dissemination could be more detailed; the list of organisations or institutions to contact appears quite vague or not well aligned to the environmental health and toxicology field, whilst if institutions are approached on the basis of co-authors' knowledge of such institutions, this may introduce bias in the sample of respondents.	We added several more organisations which we intend to approach. The lists of organisations provided are intended to provide examples, rather than being exhaustive - we would like as many respondents to share their views as possible.
9. It would be useful to indicate in this protocol what is the target number of respondents.	We agree. However, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first project looking at this issue. It is therefore difficult to estimate how many individuals will respond. It may come down to a few factors, with some of those in our control, e.g. the timing of the survey (we will hold off with survey dissemination until the Northern Hemisphere summer holidays are over, for example), and some of them outside of our control (e.g., the level of enthusiasm and snowballing). We would like as many responses as possible, of course.
10. Piloting of the survey has been included and is a strength.	Thank you very much.
11. Comment on Content Question 5: It would be helpful to know whether these sources are paid sources (e.g. ToxPlanet) or available for free.	Thank you for this suggestion. We rephrased the question as follows: "5. What sources do you search to identify grey literature for inclusion in your evidence syntheses on EHT topics? Please indicate (if possible) whether those sources are free to access or require payment."
12. Suggestions for potential additional questions: a. On average, how much time is taken or allotted to search for grey literature? b. Was this considered time well spent? c. Overall, did searching for grey literature benefit your systematic review? (i.e. Were key data identified? Were supporting information identified?)	We agree these are excellent questions, but we have made a deliberate decision to keep the survey brief to encourage high levels of participation, and have therefore been forced to forego many questions we also wanted to ask. Question (c) will probably be addressed by content question 3 (why do you include grey literature in your EHT syntheses).
13. For the thematic analysis, further details would improve the clarity of intended methods.	Thank you, we agree. We provide information about the specific changes we made, below.

<p>a. For example, will you be using software such as NVivo? b. Will you be coding prespecified themes or identifying emerging themes? If the latter, how many iterations of coding will be necessary to identify and agree on emerging themes? If the former, what are the themes you are anticipating? c. Would you expect coders to use/identify similar codes, and is it reasonable to do so given the interpretive nature of the method? d. Will you resolve discrepancies in coding between the two coders?</p>	<p>We added this information to the manuscript. We would like to use NVivo, but it is not available to all of the team members, so we indicated an option of either NVivo or Excel. We will adopt the inductive approach (emerging themes). We provided a 5-stage process that we think should work - it's an adapted version of a process previously used by one of the authors. As with systematic review screening and data extractions - discrepancies will be resolved by consensus.</p>
<p>14. The planned analyses are described succinctly.</p>	<p>Thank you very much.</p>
<p>15. It is not clear whether, if data permits to calculate the differences in proportions between respondents based on participant characteristics, these differences in proportion will be statistically tested for significance.</p>	<p>Statistical analysis of proportion differences can only be meaningfully conducted if the number of survey participants is sufficiently high and well distributed over the answer categories. As we cannot anticipate any of this, we decided to keep the analyses purely descriptive.</p>
<p>16. I would avoid using the word "reviewers" for authors of SRs - it may be confusing in relation to the peer-review process.</p>	<p>We have generally stuck to the (admittedly bit clunky) 'systematic review and other evidence synthesis' nomenclature throughout, and we think this largely avoids the issue. The alternative we had considered was 'evidence synthesisers' but whilst this term has been used (and we do use it once), it's not in general use, and it is (at least to our ears) possibly even more clunky.</p>
<p>17. You have included a statement about provision of data for the protocol itself but do not state whether you will make survey data available. The open-ended responses will be anonymised if necessary, which seems to suggest you intend to do so. Please clarify.</p>	<p>We intend to make both quantitative and qualitative data available. We added this clarification to the manuscript.</p>
<p>18. See previous comment about the declaration of interests. While most co-authors have provided informative and detailed declarations of interests, there are a few exceptions. The purpose of the declaration of interests is not to declare conflicts of interest, but to identify interests that may be conflicts in order that such interests can be managed by the research team.</p>	<p>We have noted that some disclosures are more extensive than others. We queried those co-authors who provided more concise forms about additional disclosures, however, they did not feel they had anything to add.</p>
<p>19. I would suggest you amend the title to make sure it clearly reflects that this is a protocol for a planned study rather than the results of the study themselves.</p>	<p>We retitled the manuscript to make this clearer. The new title is: 'Grey literature' in systematic reviews and evidence syntheses on Environmental Health & Toxicology topics: a survey protocol</p>